

LEXICAL PROCESSING OF BILINGUAL MEMORY IN TRANSLATION OF "PRIDE AND PREJUDICE" FROM ENGLISH INTO UZBEK

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Annotation: In this article, the translations of literary work “Pride and Prejudice” are discussed and lexical, grammatical features are classified into language categories. According to recent research and translation works, the structure of language in both English and Uzbek language are described with appropriate examples.

Key words: bilingual memory, translation, lexicology, paraphrase, language, grammar, synonym.

"Pride and prejudice" is one of the most significant masterpieces of English author Jane Austin. In this novel, love story of Elizabeth Benet, who is daughter of village peasant and Fitzwilliam Darcy, who is came from rich family, are described.

This magnificent work was translated different languages around the world and even now it has so many readers with their great interest. This article aims to compare, to analyze and to find idiomatic phrases, metaphors and idioms in “Pride and prejudice” book. Pride and Prejudice is a novel that frequently used idioms with metaphors. The reader understands that Mary is not referring to a literal ocean tide. She is using the word metaphorically. In addition to, it helps to identify what do these idioms mean and how many are there? According to meanings of them they were used coherently in this work, and one by one we will know about their meanings. These idiomatic phrases, metaphors and idioms serve to describe all scenes of work naturally, and they help to understand and to be a page turner. However, when we translate them other languages without knowing the meaning of idioms fully it reacts to readers differently, so while translating we must comb their meanings again and again. It’s known that while we are using idiomatic phrases or metaphors there are some similarities and differences between Uzbek and English

languages. According to the contexts we mostly use proper idioms when we compose works such as novel. Here you may perceive some of what: those are transparent idioms, semi-transparent idioms, semi-opaque idioms, and opaque idioms. Transparent idioms are those idioms which are easy to comprehend its constituent meaning. Semi-transparent idioms are the idioms that usually have metaphorical meaning and their constituent parts have a little role in comprehending the whole meaning of the expression.

EXAMPLES:

- 1) „*Let at last*“ means finally has been rent. – *Nihoyat*
- 2) „*Listening at the door*“ means listening to other conversation in Secret.- *Gap poylamoq*
- 3) „*Design in*“ means goal/purpose. – *Maqsad, niyat*
- 4) „*Good heavens*“ means oh god. - *Xudo haqqi.*
- 5) „*Poor nerve*“ means mentality. – *Tafakkur*
- 6) „*Poppy cock*“ means non-sensible man/woman.- *Hissiz inson*
- 7) „*Catch your eye*“ means interesting to see. – *Ko'zga yaqin*
- 8) „*Watch your tongue*“ means speaks carefully. – *Tilga ehtiyot bo'lmoq*
- 9) „*The painted peacocks*“ means a noble man/ noble woman who like to wear beautiful thing. – *Tovus misol yasangan*
- 10) „*Take the veil*“ means become a nun.- *Hijobga kirmoq*

A bunch of phrases, Idioms and metaphors are given above. As we compare them between two languages, there are some Uzbek idioms in common with English idioms.

Examples:

1. “*Not if I can help it*“ means a polite way of saying no/rejection. “*Aybga buyurmaysiz*”
2. „*To lavish upon one's partner*“ means give so many things to Other person in order to gain their affections. “*Laganbardorlik qilish*”

3. „*Be witched me, body, and soul*” means in love with me. “*Aql-u xushimni yo‘qotdim*”

4. “*Fallen sister*” means a girl who ruined up her reputation in the society. *Hammani oldida “Obro‘yini bir pul qildi”*

5. „*I’ve been so blind*” means not seeing the truth. “*Ko‘zim ko‘r bo‘lgan ekan*”, *avvalroq anglamadim.*

Prepositions, the object of our analysis, are the units that reflect the substantial potential of the English language and express specific grammatical meaning. Due to the fact that prepositions are adequate means for auxiliary words in Uzbek, and Uzbek auxiliary words are equal to cases both in the meaning and function, proportionality and disproportionality between them plays an important role when translating prepositions. Generally, synonymy of cases and auxiliary words in the Uzbek language is one of the possibilities of the Uzbek language to render the meanings of prepositions.

See the examples:

*Why, my dear, you must know, Mrs. Long says that Netherfield is taken **by** a young man of large fortune **from** the north of England; that he came down on Monday in a chaise and four to see the place, and was so much delighted with it, that he agreed **with** Mr. Morris immediately; that he is to take possession **before** Michaelmas, and some of his servants are to be in the house **by** the end of next week.*

We see that in the above text, the prepositions by, from, with, before are used, the prepositions and the texts they come in are translated into Uzbek as follows:

– *Uni eshitding azizim, – davom etdi missis Bennet.- Missis Longing aytishicha, Nezerfildni shimoliy angliyalik juda ham boy bir yigit **ijaraga** olganmish. Dushanba kuni u to‘rtta otga qo‘shilgan karetda kelib pomestyeni ko‘ribdi va joy unga shunaqa yoqibdiki, o‘sha zahotiyoq, mister Morris **bilan** ijara haqida kelishib olibdi. O‘sha yigit Maixaylovo **kunigacha** ko‘chib kelmoqchi emish, kelasi haftaning **oxirlarida** esa xizmatkorlaridan kimdir kelarmish.*

The matter includes the conclusion to the perception of translation of stylistic devices and expressive means into foreign language through the distinction of both language units, linguistic, extra-linguistic and stylistic aspects. The main criteria, the term of equivalence in translation is regarded as a specific, multi-functional approach which has been chosen in transmission of stylistic units as proper equivalent, sub-equivalent and non-equivalent or descriptive-neutral method of conveying the perception of stylistic devices into translating language. And with the help of Jane Austin's best work "Pride and Prejudice" appropriate translation examples are described briefly and successfully.

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